

MDF Recovery

Closed Loop Solution for the MDF Industry

Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) is found in every home, office, and retail environment. Despite its popularity, it is considered unrecyclable. MDF Recovery (MDFR) is a world-first technology economically recovering wood fibres from used MDF, creating a sustainable, low-cost, raw material.

Highlights of innovation features

- The MDFR recovery process is the first scalable approach to reclaim MDF board fibres from resin enabling their reuse as a raw material for the manufacturing of new boards.
- The process replaces the two most energy intensive stages of the manufacture of MDF from virgin timber, steaming and refining, therefore reducing the embedded CO₂ of the finished product.
- The recovered fibre is of the same high quality as virgin wood fibre and provides a feedstock to the manufacturers of MDF board, insulation products and formable packing materials.

Over 100 million m³ of MDF are produced each year across the globe. Around 20% is wasted during the manufacturing process and in the supply chain, not including post-consumer 'end-of-life' MDF, resulting in a huge potential market for MDFR's production of new recycled material that reduces pressure on standing forests.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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